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Report on Training Activities**

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Executive Summary

This deliverable gives an overview of the multitude of training activities that were offered in the first 24 months of the RIANA project. These trainings aim to educate both internal staff and external users. The breadth of training activities reflects the enthusiasm of the RIANA partners to transfer their knowledge and skills, and the success of the activities mirrors the thirst for knowledge of the scientific user community.

The most important training activities include:

- Training of internal staff at RIANA research infrastructures with a focus on the Smart Science Cluster
- Training of external users accessing RIANA research infrastructures
- Horizontal training for staff and users

1. Introduction

Cutting-edge research goes hand in hand with education and training. This is particularly the case for fast-evolving fields like nanoscience and nanotechnology – the fields of research in which RIANA offers access to research infrastructures (RI). Accordingly, education and training play a distinctive role in RIANA.

Work package 5 takes care of the training needs for the Junior Scientists and facility staff as well as users. On short term, this ensures highest profit from the new customized and multi-disciplinary access to high-end research infrastructures in RIANA, and on the long term, this enables sustainability in research and development for prospering research and development in the competitive fields of nanoscience and nanotechnology by educating the next generation of innovators.

A training platform is established to strengthen researchers by increasing their scientific excellence along with knowledge on intellectual property (IP) to enable efficient technology transfer from innovations to sustainable business operation. Emphasis lies on cross-disciplinary training through fostering the interaction between the RI networks. Furthermore, education opportunities are offered to users that seek to explore new techniques within the broad RIANA portfolio of instruments and data analysis.

The training and education activities are broken down into the following tasks:

- Task 5.1: The *internal staff training* focuses on Junior Scientists that are organized in the Smart Science Cluster (WP2), offering a staff exchange program and regular tutorial webinars on technical and scientific topics as well as on non-technical topics such as on IP rights.
- Task 5.2: The *external training for users* includes pre-access training visits and specific online trainings for software and data analysis. Furthermore, mutual exchange of the diverse user community is fostered through RIANA user meetings.
- Task 5.3: The *horizontal training program* includes on the one side tutorial webinars and training schools that are offered by RIANA itself, and on the other side schools that are offered by partners of the RIANA networks, leveraging synergies between research infrastructures and European projects.

All training activities of RIANA are thoroughly discussed within the RIANA Executive Board and aligned with the other WPs.

2. Task 5.1: Internal training within RIANA

The aim of Task 5.1 is to involve, connect, and strengthen the existing communities of staff researchers in nanotechnology to build a cohort of interdisciplinary Junior Scientists and staff members with an impact far beyond the RIANA project duration. To achieve this objective, two complementary sub-tasks address different aspects of internal training and knowledge exchange.

Task 5.1.1 provides targeted training to Junior Scientists and staff members through the Staff Exchange program, while the “Invite an Expert” initiative supports scientific exchange and strengthens collaboration between the RIANA partner networks. In addition, Task 5.2.1 contributes to the internal training objectives by organizing webinars presenting the facilities, their techniques and capabilities, and cross-cutting topics such as intellectual property rights (IPR) and patenting or data management following the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable, see also deliverable D6.2).

Task 5.1.1: Staff exchanges

Calls for two complementary programs have been published under Task 5.1.1: (a) the Staff Exchange program and (b) the “Invite an Expert” initiative. While the Staff Exchange program focuses on providing hands-on, on-site training for Junior Scientists and staff members at partner institutions, the “Invite an Expert” initiative promotes scientific exchange at a strategic level by facilitating invited talks and expert visits between networks. The evaluation and selection procedure has been implemented and is fully operational, ensuring transparent and efficient processing of applications.

- (a) The first Staff Exchange call was published on the RIANA website in November 2024 (Milestone M13) and communicated directly to the stake holders via internal mailing lists and announcements at RIANA meetings. Following this call, two applications were received, which corresponds to 10% of the expected 21 exchanges. One exchange visit has been successfully completed, and the corresponding financial support has been processed. The second exchange visit is scheduled to take place before the RIANA annual meeting in March 2026. These exchanges directly contribute to RIANA’s objective of strengthening cross-network technical expertise and ensuring high-quality support for inter-network user projects.

To further facilitate participation and lower administrative barriers, a revised call document has been prepared and is currently being finalized for publication on the RIANA website. In analogy to the rolling call for transnational access to RIs, the continuous call format is expected to increase participation and flexibility needed for staff exchange.

As the recruitment of Junior Scientists has been completed across all RIANA partner facilities, increased participation in the Staff Exchange program is anticipated in the next reporting period. This expectation is further supported by the growing number of user applications received within RIANA, which increases the need for Junior Scientists to develop complementary technical expertise and strengthens their motivation to participate in inter-network training activities.

- (b) The call for the “Invite an Expert” initiative was published concurrently with the Staff Exchange call (Milestone M12). While no expert exchanges have been completed to date, initial interest has

been expressed, and applications are expected in connection with upcoming scientific conferences and network meetings in the next reporting period.

In the next reporting period, increased participation in both programs is expected, which is supported by the continuous call format and the growing operational maturity of RIANA. These activities will further strengthen technical expertise, promote inter-network collaboration, and enhance the quality of user support across the RIANA infrastructure.

Task 5.1.2: Internal webinars

Within this task, two objectives were pursued:

- (a) Internal talks/webinars on different topics target specifically Junior Scientists and staff scientists at RIANA infrastructures. The topics are widespread from science and technology to unconscious gender/minority bias, intellectual property rights, and FAIR data / big data management. The cooperation with the Junior Scientists from WP2 was critical for the successful launch of this webinar series.

To achieve this objective, all representatives of the RIANA networks were contacted to contribute with seminars and discussions related to the topics presented above. Announcements about the webinars were sent to RIANA members and dissipated via the RIANA YouTube channel as illustrated in Fig. 1. While these webinars were planned to be internal in beginning, we decided to publish those that are of general interest and for which the presenter has approved recording.

Figure 1: Example of a RIANA webinar held as training of internal staff and the user community. The recording is dissipated and made long-term available through the RIANA YouTube channel <https://www.youtube.com/@RIANAproject>.

A list of the webinars and discussions is presented below:

- *“Attosecond Interferometry,”* Nirit Dudovich, (Weizmann Institute of Science, Israel)
 - *“Laser illumination in classical and super-resolution multicolor microscopy,”* Adrien Mau (Abbelight, France).
 - *“Compressive Raman imaging: a computational framework for high-speed chemical microscopy,”* Hilton B. de Aguiar (CNRS, Laboratoire Kastler Brossel and Ecole Normale Supérieure, France)
 - *“From Telescopes to Fusion Powerplants: Real-Time Adaptive Optics for High-Power Lasers,”* Jonas B. Ohland (GSI Helmholtz Center for Heavy Ion Research, Germany)
 - *“Laser-surface processing for green Hydrogen and energy storage applications,”* Panagiotis A. Loukakos (IESL-FORTH, Greece)
 - *“Boosting Multiphoton 3D Printing for Biomedical Engineering: Small Features, High Impact,”* Irina Alexandra Paun (INFLPR/CETAL, Romania)
 - *“Glass Drilling with Femtosecond Laser in GHz-Burst Mode,”* Inka Manek-Hönninger (University of Bordeaux, CNRS-CELIA, France)
 - *“Exploring Plasma and its Use in Nanofabrication: Etching,”* Andrei Avram (National Institute for R&D in Microtechnologies – IMT Bucharest, Romania)
 - *“Additive-Subtractive Synergy in Ultrafast Digital Manufacturing: Tunable Femtosecond-to-Picosecond Laser Processing for Highly Selective Ablation and Printing in Thin-Film Electronics and Photovoltaic Applications,”* Catalin Constantinescu (LP3-Aix-Marseille Université, CNRS, France)
- (b) Two in-person innovation contests are conducted in the framework of the RIANA annual meetings after years 2 and 4. These short in-person events target Junior Scientists who have an innovative idea and seek to develop an elevator pitch and business plan for the exploitation of their innovation. The first Innovation Contest has been launched 2025 (Milestone M14) with the announcement shown in Fig. 2.

After having submitted written proposals, the applicants for the first RIANA Innovation Contest presented their project ideas to the RIANA Executive Board (EB) in their first meeting in 2026. The proposals were thoroughly discussed by the EB members, and two proposals were selected for funding. In the follow-up, EB members with expertise in innovation gave feedback to the financial planning and pitch. These suggestions were incorporated in the final presentation of the two winners that were announced during the Annual Meeting 2026 and on LinkedIn (see Fig. 3), fulfilling the RIANA Milestone 5.3.

Congratulations to Dr. Simona Bianco and Dr. Jakub Jagielski for winning the first RIANA Innovation Contest!

CALL FOR INNOVATION CONTESTS-
1ST EDITION

**Funded by
the European Union**

OBJECTIVE

Don't miss the chance and take the floor! Present your idea within the Innovation Contest- First Edition initiative of the RIANA's project - just apply, no pressure!! Not only will you gain helpful insights and experience to start your future business, but you will also have the chance to promote and push your idea forward

Program Details

 Opening: The submission of applications for the **Innovation Contest - First Edition is open till December 15th, 2025.**

Aiming to unlock the entrepreneurial mindset of Junior Scientists, the **Innovation Contest** is taking place within the "Training and Education" section of the RIANA project. This action is an opportunity for Junior Scientists from all RIANA partners to develop innovative ideas and to find solutions for challenges in the field of **Nanoscience and Nanotechnologies**.

To boost their innovative potential, the first **Innovation Contest** targets Junior Scientists who want to develop a business plan and elevator pitch for their innovation. The proposals will be highlighted during the **RIANA Annual Meeting 2026**. The best proposal will be decided through a competitive selection process and will be awarded with funds for the further development of the presented innovative idea.

Figure 2: Announcement of the first RIANA Innovation Contest to support the innovative ideas of Junior Scientists.

RIANA - project

2mo • Edited •

 We are proud to announce the winners of the 1st **RIANA - project** Innovation Contest Dr. **Simona Bianco** and Dr. **Jakub Jagielski**!

The contest aimed to unlock the entrepreneurial potential of Junior Scientists, challenging participants to develop innovative business plans and solutions in nanoscience and nanotechnology.

Dr. **Simona Bianco** presented a project that offers a bottom-up approach to designing peptide-based hybrid materials enhanced with nanofillers and developing novel methods for their in situ characterisation at **MAX IV Laboratory**. These innovative materials will be engineered to function as stimuli-responsive soft actuators for applications in soft robotics and flexible sensors.

Dr. **Jakub Jagielski** presented work on "Bioactive Lipid Cuboplexes: A Novel Synergistic Strategy for Resensitising Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria". The project involves a multifunctional system designed to disable bacterial defence mechanisms, specifically efflux pumps. This strategy aims to resensitise resistant bacteria to antibiotics that had previously lost their efficacy, thereby restoring their therapeutic effectiveness.

Congratulations to the winners 🎉🎉🎉 !

[#innovation](#) [#BusinessPlan](#) [#antibiotics](#) [#bacteria](#) [#NovelMaterials](#) [#lipids](#) [#anofillers](#) [#insitu](#)

Figure 3: Announcement of the winners of the first RIANA Innovation Contest on LinkedIn.

3. Task 5.2: External training to academic and industrial Users

In Task 5.2 training actions are implemented aiming at the development of additional skills for the professional and career prospect enhancement of users originating from both the academic and the industrial sector. The training actions are at the same time expected to facilitate and maximize the research and innovation output of the user projects and help to prepare competitive new ones. The training actions by representatives of the RI networks increase awareness for the added value offered by the joint use of infrastructures. Vice versa, the attractiveness of the RIANA infrastructures is also enhanced and the dissemination of the project results facilitated.

The external training actions are organized in three sub-tasks: Task 5.2.1 covers RIANA Users Meetings, Task 5.2.2 enables pre-access user training for efficient use of valuable transnational access, and Task 5.2.3 offers online software training, which is particularly for the planning of experiments and the analysis of data obtained through transnational access.

Task 5.2.1: RIANA User Meetings

The 1st RIANA Users Meeting has taken place at the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH) in Heraklion, Greece, 17 – 18 March 2026, co-located with the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting 18 – 21 March 2026 to profit from synergies. The invitation for the Users Meeting was sent to a broader community, including the local academic community, which was particularly appreciated by young scientists that have otherwise limited possibilities to discuss their research ideas at the international level in person.

The meeting included sessions with oral presentations of existing and prospective RIANA Users presenting their exciting research. A list of the high-level presentations is presented in Fig. 4. The scientific User presentations were followed by a poster session with many contributions from Users and infrastructures. It triggered numerous ideas for further research projects, and we witnessed the nucleation of new RIANA proposals resulting from the exchange between Users and infrastructure representatives.

During the second day of the Users meeting, there was a joint session between the 1st RIANA Users Meeting and the 2nd RIANA Annual Meeting: the Smart Science Cluster presented the available RIANA techniques and thus informed existing and prospective Users about possibilities to realize their scientific ideas through RIANA. With 17¹ excellent presentations by active and prospective Users and about 65 attendants, we consider the 1st RIANA Users Meeting a full success.

¹ One of the 18 scheduled presentations could not be given due to the war in Iran.

Chair <i>Alexey Masimenko (SOLARIS, LEAPS)</i>			
09:00-10:40 Opening-Welcome-USERS Presentations			
09:00	Opening	Wellcome	Panagiotis Loukakos (FORTH)
	Intro	RIANA Science Service for TNA Users	Regina Ciancio (AREA), Jummi Laishram (AREA), Ryan Yang (HZDR)
09:20	O1	Multidisciplinary approach to analyses of particulate matter	Lucyna Samek (AGH University of Krakow, Krakow)
09:40	O2	Multi-technique Investigation of Doped-BSCCO High-Temperature Superconductors: How RIANA Bridges African Research to European Facilities	Mustafa Shalaby (Egyptian Atomic Energy Authority, Egypt)
10:00	O3 (REMOTE)	Advanced 3D surface and interface characterization of functional materials using RIANA facilities	Ebrahim Gholami Hatam (Malayer University, Iran)
10:20	O4	Multi-modal Electron Microscopy of 3D FEBID Racetrack Memory	Sameh Okasha, Gregor Hlawacek, Ryan Yang, Attila Kákay, András Kovács, Rafal Dunin-Borkowski, Trevor P. Almeida (University of Glasgow, UK)
10:40	O5	Multiphoton Polymerization: An Enabling Technology for Applications from Photonics to Tissue Engineering	Maria Farsari (FORTH-IESL)
11:00-11:20 <i>Coffee break</i>			
Chair <i>Octavian-Gabriel Simionescu (IMT, EUROnanoLAB)</i>			
11:20-12:40 USERS Presentations			
11:20	O6 (REMOTE)	Laser-Matter Interaction Driven Formation of Anisotropic Gold Nanoworms with Tunable Optical and Catalytic Properties	Ayesha Noor, Hamza Qayyum (COMSATS University Islamabad, Pakistan)
11:40	O7	Microwave-Plasma Synthesis and Multimodal Characterization of Magnetic Iron Oxide Nanoparticles	F.J. Fernández-Alonso, S. Caspani, A. Cruz, A. Maximenko, D. Navas, M. Manso-Silván, C. Tavares De Sousa (Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Spain)
12:00	O8 (REMOTE)	Surface compositional effects on nanodot patterning produced on silicon by ion-beam irradiation with metal co-deposition	L. Vázquez, F.J. Palomares, E. Herguedas, E. Tosi (Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid-CSIC, Spain)
12:20	O9 (REMOTE)	Co-Doping-Regulated Oxygen Redox in Cobalt-Free Li-Rich Cathodes	Rui Wang (University of Cambridge, UK)
12:40	O10	Multiscale Modelling of Surface Patterning via Ultrashort Laser Pulses	George Tsibidis, Emmanuel Stratakis (FORTH-IESL)
13:00- 14:20 <i>Lunch</i>			
Chair <i>George Tsibidis (FORTH-IESL)</i>			
14:20-17:40 USERS Presentations			
14:20	O11	Grayscale Multiphoton Lithography for Advanced Optical Elements in Microsphere-Assisted Microscopy	G. Zyla, D. Ladika, I. Kassamakov, B. Loppinet, and Maria Farsari (Vilnius University, Lithuania)
14:40	O12	Atomistic Modeling and Ion-Irradiation Experiments for Understanding Helium-Induced Embrittlement in RAFM Steels	Aneta Ustrzycka (Polish Academy of Sciences, Poland)
15:00	O13	Self-Assembly of Star and Amphiphilic Responsive Anisotropic Colloids	A. Francisco Meija, S. Bianco, T. Plivelic, E. Grelet and J.J. Crassous (RWTH Aachen University)
15:20	O14	Efficient hydrogen-boron fusion process from cluster – target interaction, coupled with nanostructured alpha detection	C. Daponta, S.D. Moustazis, A. Klini, M. Farsari and P. Loukakos (Technical University of Crete, Greece)
15:40-16:00 <i>Coffee break</i>			
Chair <i>Gordon Zyla (Vilnius University, Lithuania)</i>			
16:00	O15	Application of innovative techniques for monitoring Nano-(Bio)- Micro- Plastics interactions with Marine Bacteria and Diatoms	Constantinos Varotsis (Cyprus University of Tehnology, Cyprus)
16:20	O16	Modified Nickel Foam-Based Electrodes for Alkaline Hydrogen Evolution and Energy Storage	Ioannis Poimenidis, Michalis Konsolakis (Technical University of Crete, Greece)
17:00	O17	Macromolecular Design Strategies for High-Performance Single-ion Electrolytes for Solid-State Batteries	Emmanuel Glynos (University of Crete & FORTH-IESL)
17:20	O18 (REMOTE)	How to prepare a RIANA project proposal	Catalin Constantinescu (CNRS, Laboratoire LP3, France)

Figure 4: Program of the oral presentations during the 1st RIANA Users Meeting 17 March 2026 at FORTH in Heraklion, Crete.

Task 5.2.2: Pre-access User training visits

The aim of this Task is to offer younger or less experienced members of User teams the opportunity to get acquainted with the infrastructure of the hosting institution, in advance of the actual transnational access provision. This enhances the User experience by increasing their awareness about the facility instruments and the acquisition and analysis methods to make best use of valuable experiment access.

Users can select whether they wish to profit from the pre-access training option during the proposal submission in the ARIA portal. The cooperation with WP3 was critical for the setting up the workflow enabling pre-access User training visits.

So far, 2 formal pre-access training requests were received:

- PID 38029 (Sameh Okasha)
- PID 39347 (Mustafa Shalaby)

Note that this number is low due to underreporting: at many infrastructures, it is common for users to arrive early and get familiarized with setups beyond a formal pre-access training, and the Smart Science Cluster does a marvelous job preparing on-site access through online meetings. Nevertheless, we expect to receive more requests for pre-access training as the number of academic access proposals increases and more users from academia and industry are hosted at research infrastructures.

Task 5.2.3: Online software training

The online software training tools consist of interactive online software and theoretical simulations/algorithms for training on the optimal use of specific instruments and setups on the one hand, and of data analysis software on the other hand. The tools will be made available to Users via the RIANA webpage.

- (1) FORTH has started preparing a first tool: a machine-learning based predictive tool providing maps of zones where laser-matter interaction results in the creation of nanostructures in additive and subtractive laser-processing.

Femtosecond pulsed lasers are widely used for micro- and nanoscale patterning. Efficient material processing requires accurate knowledge of thermal and optical responses following ultrashort laser irradiation. While many studies have explored laser-induced thermal effects such as ablation, phase transitions and material damage, the combined optical and thermal behavior of thin films with thicknesses near the optical penetration depth remains largely unexplored. Furthermore, identifying laser conditions that induce laser-induced periodic surface structures (LIPSS) is also crucial for fabricating biomimetic functional patterns for industrial applications. Current analyses often rely on specialized algorithms or expensive software with limited access. The Graphical User Interface of the tool under development aims to enable a user-friendly evaluation of LIPSS formation and optothermal responses in various metals (Au, Ag, Cu, Al, Ni, Ti, Cr, stainless steel, W, Pt, Mo) on three substrates (Si, SiO₂, soda-lime glass) and free-standing films. It uses a physical model combining optical absorption and thermal effects via the Two-Temperature Model allowing assessment of photon energy, film thickness, pulse duration, pulse separation and peak fluence.

Currently details of the algorithm and web interface are being worked out. The tool will be tested with real Users of the laser infrastructure at FORTH before making it available to entire RIANA.

- (2) HZDR has contributed pyIBA,² an open-source Python library developed by Dr. Miguel Sequeira (HZDR) for Ion Beam Analysis (IBA) data management and analysis. pyIBA provides a user-friendly, object-oriented interface to the Ion Beam Data Format (IDF) standard and supports the creation, editing, processing, and analysis of IBA data in line with FAIR data principles, with integration into common scientific Python libraries. Documentation with usage examples is available online.

² <https://github.com/m-sequeira/pyIBA>

4. Task 5.3: Horizontal training and educational actions

Task 5.3.1 aims to design, organize, and deliver high-level in-person training schools addressing the needs of early-career and experienced researchers in nanoscience and advanced materials. The training schools are conceived as integrative events combining lectures, practical demonstrations, and direct interaction with RIANA infrastructures. A key objective is to foster cross-disciplinary skills, promote responsible and open access to RIANA facilities, and strengthen the European research community around nanoscience, advanced materials, and related research infrastructures.

Task 5.3.2 is dedicated to the development of RIANA technology webinars and the establishment of an associated online database of educational and training resources. The main objective is to provide open, easily accessible, and high-quality digital content that complements the in-person training schools from Task 5.3.1 and supports continuous learning within the RIANA community. The webinars are designed to present RIANA technologies, methodologies, and access opportunities. They highlight best practices and showcase recent advances in nanoscience and advanced materials, reaching a broad audience beyond physical events, including potential new users.

Task 5.3.1: Training schools

During the first 24 months of the project, Task 5.3.1 has been successfully implemented through the preparation and organisation of RIANA training schools, in close coordination with other RIANA work packages and partner infrastructures. The training schools were designed to complement the RIANA Transnational Access activities providing participants with both theoretical background and practical insight into state-of-the-art techniques.

The 1st RIANA Training School was held from 8 – 11 September 2025³ at Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ), Germany. It was hosted by the Ernst-Ruska-Center for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons (ERC) and organized by Rafal Dunin-Borkowski (director of ERC), Geneviève Wilbs (assistant at ERC), Catalin Constantinescu (CNRS-LP3), and Inka Manek-Hönninger (task leader T5.3.1, CNRS-CELIA). This first training school offered a large overview on different techniques and application fields in nanoscience and nanotechnology, with high-level lectures given by 13 different speakers. The school was attended by 26 participants of 13 different nationalities and from 10 different affiliation countries, and 54% of the participants identified themselves as female.

Particular attention was paid to the balance between lectures, tutorials, and interactive sessions, enabling participants to directly engage with RIANA experts and access providers. The schools also served as networking platforms, encouraging collaboration between young researchers, senior scientists, and infrastructure operators. The program included lectures on laser-induced periodic surface structuring (LIPSS), synchrotron and free electron lasers for nanomaterials characterization, thin-film processing for additive manufacturing, neutron scattering including applications and simulations, ion beam techniques, optical microscopy and rheology, evanescent illumination and Rayleigh scattering, as well as electron microscopy and its applications. Moreover, visits of the Helmholtz Nano Facility (HNF), the Supercomputer (JSC), ERC with demonstrations of electron

³ <https://riana-project.eu/2025/09/12/1st-riana-training-school-on-nanoscience-and-nanotechnology-successfully-finished/>

microscopy, and the Institute of Biological Information Processing (IBI-4 and IBI-7) including hand-on trainings were extremely appreciated by all participants and lecturers.

Figure 5: Group photo 1st RIANA Training School (left) and winners of the Best Poster Award (right).

The satisfaction survey at the end of the training school resulted in overwhelming feedback on the scientific program concerning quality, content, and quantity. The organisation of the training school was also very well received, and housing of all participants in the same hotel with a bus shuttle transfer to the FZJ every day were particularly appreciated. The vast majority (88%) of the participants are interested in attending the 2nd RIANA training School which is planned to take place 1 – 4 June 2026 at the Ion Beam Center of the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf (HZDR, Germany).⁴

Task 5.3.1 shows strong synergy with other RIANA activities, notably with WP2 and WP3, by aligning the training content with the available experimental techniques and access modes offered by RIANA infrastructures; with WP6, through dissemination and outreach actions, ensuring wide visibility of the training opportunities and results; with WP5 internal tasks, by contributing educational material and recorded content that can be reused in webinars and online resources. This integrated approach ensures that the training schools do not stand alone but rather act as a core element of the RIANA user support and capacity-building strategy.

Key highlights of Task 5.3.1 during the first two years of RIANA include the successful organisation and delivery of RIANA training schools with strong international participation; high engagement of early-career researchers, contributing to skills development and long-term community building; direct exposure of participants to RIANA infrastructures and access procedures, lowering entry barriers for future users. No major unexpected issues were encountered during this period, and minor organisational challenges related to scheduling and logistics were efficiently handled through close coordination among partners.

⁴ <https://www.hzdr.de/db/Cms?pOid=35354&pNid=1984&pLang=en>

Task 5.3.2: RIANA technology webinars and database

A structured webinar program covering RIANA technologies was set up and successfully implemented. The RIANA technology webinars are jointly organized and coordinated with partners from different RIANA networks and infrastructures, ensuring broad thematic coverage and scientific excellence. The webinars are delivered in an online format and feature presentations by RIANA experts and infrastructure providers. They focus on specific techniques, platforms, and use cases, with interactive question-and-answer sessions with participants. All webinars are recorded and made publicly available through the RIANA website and the official RIANA YouTube channel. This approach ensures long-term availability of the content and maximises outreach and impact.

Figure 6: RIANA webinars are published on the consortium webpage and are available on the official RIANA YouTube channel.⁵

In parallel with the webinar activities, Task 5.3.2 contributes to the development and continuous enrichment of the RIANA online educational material repository. The user-friendly database⁶ is embedded in the RIANA webpage and includes recorded webinar videos, presentation slides with complementary documentation. This digital resource plays a key role in supporting self-learning and preparation for RIANA access applications and is continuously updated with new webinars and curated educational resources linked to RIANA technologies and infrastructures.

Towards the end of the project, the online database will be transferred into a FAIR database.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/@RIANAproject>

⁶ <https://riana-project.eu/educational-material/>

Concerning the integration and synergy within the RIANA consortium activities, task 5.3.2 is closely linked to Task 5.3.1 and other RIANA dissemination and training activities. Content generated during training schools is reused and adapted for webinars and online materials, ensuring consistency and efficient use of resources. Strong links are also maintained with WP6 to maximize visibility and dissemination of the webinar series.

The main achievements of Task 5.3.2 during the first two years of RIANA include the successful launch and regular delivery of RIANA technology webinars; establishment of a sustainable online repository of educational materials; increased visibility of RIANA technologies and infrastructures at the European level. No significant risks or unexpected issues were identified for this task during the reporting period. The online format proved robust and adaptable, enabling broad participation and long-term impact.

5. Outlook

Broken down by individual tasks, the following actions related to training are coming up next:

- **Task 5.1.1**

The call for staff exchanges will remain open as a rolling call and applications will be evaluated immediately upon reception. Similarly, applications for the “invite an expert” initiative can be submitted anytime. While we did not receive any application yet, we expect to receive applications in the next period thanks to increased dissemination activities.

- **Task 5.1.2**

The internal webinars have been successfully initiated and will be continued. Also, the “2nd Innovation Contests” will be launched in the next reporting period (Milestone M15).

- **Task 5.2.1**

The 1st Users meeting is scheduled to take place March 17 – 18, 2026. The 2nd Users Meeting will also be scheduled in the next reporting period.

- **Task 5.2.2**

Two pre-access training requests have been accepted and more are expected to be requested as the TNA access program involves more user projects.

- **Task 5.2.3**

Significant progress has been made setting up two online software training tools that are expected to be finalized within the next reporting period.

- **Task 5.3.1**

The 2nd RIANA Training School is scheduled in June 2026, and the 3rd RIANA Training School is also expected to be organized within the next reporting period.

- **Task 5.3.2**

The RIANA online educational material repository has been successfully launched and a few technical webinars have already been published in that database. More material is expected to be created by partners and uploaded in due time.

In summary, all tasks of Work Package 5 are running well within schedule. They are highly successful and productive, and we expect to deliver the described Tasks and work and fulfill the objectives as initially designed and within the planned time schedule. All tasks are well on track, no major deviations have taken place and no corrective actions are needed so far.